

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES
SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**EVALUATION OF BUCKWHEAT TO CHECK NUTRITION
VALUE, LEVEL OF CURE AND FOR THE MANAGEMENT
OF DIABETES TO INCREASE THE USE OF BUCKWHEAT
INSTEAD OF INSULIN**

¹Dr Jaza Abbas, ²Dr Humaira Qasim, ³Dr Virdah Farooq

¹Madina Teaching Hospital Faisalabad

²Quaid e Azam Medical College

³Quaid e Azam Medical College

Article Received: July 2020

Accepted: August 2020

Published: September 2020

Abstract:

Diabetes full named Diabetes mellitus is somehow genetic disorder or disease and that also effect the endocrine system which directly secretes hormones to the bloodstream and leaves very harmful effects on our body, and that disease nowadays very common in whole world. There is a plant named Buckwheat, used for the treatment of diabetes. Due to having biological properties it becomes very beneficial to control hypertension and cholesterol in a diabetic patient body and it also help the patients to improve fat of their bodies and solve their constipation issues. Some recent researches are going on to increase the level of treatment of diabetes on next level.

Keywords: Buckwheat, Fagopyrum, Polygonaceae, Tartary buckwheat, Diabetes.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Jaza Abbas,

Madina Teaching Hospital Faisalabad

QR code

Please cite this article in press Jaza Abbas et al, Evaluation Of Buckwheat To Check Nutrition Value, Level Of Cure And For The Management Of Diabetes To Increase The Use Of Buckwheat Instead Of Insulin., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

[1]Buckwheat is a type of grains used for the treatment of diabetes; Buckwheat has another name called triangle-wheat due to its shape, certainly we know it as cereal but perfectly it does not used as cereal so we named it pseudo-cereal.[2] That plant belongs to a Family (Polygonaceae) and Genus (Fagopyrum).It has limited cultivation area in Pakistan, Buckwheat wheat have abundant species but 9 of them used for agricultural projects and two of them used for the humans as a food, common buckwheat and Tartary buckwheat are the types used as food.[3] When they become cultivated, they show different ratio by using or by skipping fertilizers. So use of fertilizers help us to increase the amount of production of Buckwheat. [4]With the seeds and tissues of buckwheat we get proteins, minerals, lipids, polyphones, dietary fibers etc and are polysaccharides. [5]Now these compounds have different properties like protein we get from Buckwheat have amino acids that help to maintain diabetes by controlling the level of cholesterol and help to maintain body fat. [6]It is also helpful of the treatment of heart disease or to maintain cardiovascular issues. Main function of Buckwheat to control body sugar and help to cure the diabetic patient as it help to low-sugar level in body and reduce the use of insulin in the body. [7]Some of Diabetic patients use insulin and some of them did not use it, so if we talk about the using of insulin, the patients whose,[8] mellitus diabetes move at the severe stage doctors recommended them to use insulin but as we known approximately a big ratio in whole world is effected with the diabetes, so instead of using insulin they take tablets to decrease sugar level and also used natural things as Buckwheat is one of them to control the body sugar level. [9]About 41crore 50 lac people are effected with this disease in whole world and as it is increasing continuously, [10] it will read to the 64crore 10 lac[11].Recent researches showed that we used drugs that are approved as anti diabetic. [12]Not only helpful for mellitus diabetes but Buckwheat is also helpful for the treatment of cancer or to control level of cholesterol in the body and also helpful in neurological disorders, [13]So common and Tartary Buck wheat are the main two types used for the treatment of diabetes in humans.

METHODOLOGY:

Make able to use Buckwheat in daily life for treatment of diabetes, it first move to the laboratory, We get common wheat and Tartary wheat from skardu, Pakistan. From fields it moves to the laboratory mill to change it into the flour, A big grain testing laboratory of Pakistan, NARC located in Islamabad, there they check the moisture in the grains, crude proteins, ash and fat contents. To dry up moisture they use big ovens for Buckwheat grains, They used different methods and apparatus for fat ,protein and ash, After few hours when all these processes are completed Yao et al. method is used to change the grains into powder in 70 minutes with 60% ethanol aqueous solution at 50 C. After the process of filtration and evaporation, it stored at 4 degree centigrade before use. There was an experiment held in the NIH, (Islamabad)Pakistan, That experiment was on group of mice to check the diabetes in animals, they take 15 mice and equally divided into 3 groups, mice which was in group 1 was control diabetic animals and other two groups are those one who feed on common Buckwheat grains and others who feed on Tartary Buckwheat grains as per their body weight, they keep them in specific temperature for 12 hours with both dark and light circumstances, now after 7 days of experiment they give injections to mice and at the 4th day of injection they take their blood sample from their tail and they was able to see diabetic symptoms in their bodies ,level of sugar was high, now they kept these mice for 21 more days and treat them by giving grains of common and Tartary Buckwheat to low their sugar level. Then in within these 21 days duration after each week they took their blood test after fasting for night and they give them injection and measure sugar level with different time duration.

RESULTS:

Finally after experiment we conclude that there was no difference between ash and protein with common and Tartary buck wheat but the level of fiber ,fat and protein in Tartary buckwheat is higher them common buckwheat.

Table 1: Chemical composition of Tartary and common buckwheat

Proximate composition	Common Buckwheat	Tartary Buckwheat
Moisture%	10.61± 0.049a	10.345±0.101a
Protein%	11.90± 0.886b	13.68±0.199a
Fat%	2.396± 0.016b	3.4731±0.537a
Fiber%	9.424± 0.572b	12.034±0.709a
Ash%	2.9503 ±0.117a	2.863±0.519a
NFE%	62.62±1.906a	57.55±1.314b

We see some variations in the ratios of Common Buckwheat and Tartary Buckwheat, like moisture in Common Buckwheat is somehow different with the Tartary Buckwheat due to the change in atmosphere where these crops

grow or due to fertilizers. Now if we talk about the quality or the quantity of Buckwheat, that also have margins like due to pesticides or fertilizers or the variety of grains we used at the time of cultivation, So due to all these reasons we sometimes show changes in proteins, fats or in fibers but usually we see different researches where we see equal quality of both common Buckwheat and Tartary Buckwheat. Sometimes these differences occur in these two species of Buckwheat due to the seedling, way of seedling or the change in time period, so these are the factors or points that make them different from each other.

Table 2: Mineral composition of Tartary and common Buckwheat flour (ppm)

Mineral composition	Common Buckwheat	Tartary Buckwheat
Iron (Fe)	113.89±1.063b	127.11±1.334a
Zinc (Zn)	10.78±0.955b	13.811±0.939a
Magnesium (Mg)	1560.3±1.357b	2322.7±3.856a
Manganese (Mn)	8.473±0.512b	10.585±0.508a
Copper (Cu)	5.7267±0.447b	7.2533±0.564a

Fig 1: Antioxidant activity of common and Tartary Buckwheat flour at different concentrations.

Here in this graph we check concentration of both Common Buckwheat and Tartary Buckwheat, and we conclude that the concentration of Tartary Buckwheat was higher.

Table 3: Chemical composition of common and Tartary Buckwheat extract

Chemical composition	Common Buckwheat	Tartary Buckwheat
Carbohydrates%	0.593±0.025a	0.366±0.060b
Protein%	5.43±0.277b	6.68±0.503a
Moisture%	4.393±0.692b	5.983±0.526a

In this table, we check the chemical composition of common and Tartary Buckwheat with carbohydrates, protein and moisture, so rate of carbohydrates is higher in common buckwheat but rate of protein and moisture increase/higher in Tartary Buckwheat as compared to common Buckwheat.

Glucose lowering effect of buckwheat

Buck wheat help to control sugar level in the blood ,at the first day of experiment, the addition of glucose after alloxan was approx 67% but on the other hand, groups that contain CBE and TBE was 84% and 67%. And then by passing of days it increase gradually and reach at 139% in group 1.but in other two groups level of glucose decrease with the passage of time. So we can concluded that buckwheat help to reduce level of sugar in body.

(Fig 2)

Tolerance Test:

Here in fig 3 we can clearly see that in group 1 where control diabetic mice was present increase the level of glucose with 75 minutes but in other 2 groups it decreases at the duration of 45 and 120 min. We can check how buckwheat improve range of tolerance of glucose in mice.

(Fig 3)

There was a slight change in experimental group and control group, mice body weight was slightly increased or decreased from day one to the 21st day of experiment. Seen in fig 4.s it is defined as by using excellent quality of buckwheat help to increase body weight of experimental mice.

(Fig 4)

DISCUSSION:

(14) Level of sugar in mice body will be reduced by using Buckwheat, it helps to treat diabetes and resist use of insulin. (15) It manage cholesterol level and in whole topic we discussed that Buckwheat help us to maintain glucose level in the body as we have

(16) discussed an experiment of mice with 21 days duration to check the sugar level in mice body and then effects happen when we try to treat it with the Buckwheat, we see different stages to purify grain flour and make it able for the usage of human beings. (17) By treating diabetes with insulin harm other

body parts so we can say that it reduces our life but use of buckwheat grains or flour is very effective because it have insulin properties naturally, (18) so it does not harm to our body parts and help u to make our self-healthy.

CONCLUSION:

We concluded that buckwheat is effective for the reduction of sugar level in the body. It's a pseudo-cereal and human beings can used it to treat diabetes mellitus with the help of this plant. Main two types (common and Tartary) buckwheat are used to lower glucose level. Fagopyritol present in these seeds help to reduce the use of insulin, instead of using insulin, use buckwheat flour to control sugar level. Both of these types of Buckwheat is very help for Diabetic patients.

REFERENCES:

- Bian, J., F. Shan, Z. Tian, G. Xu, R. Lin, X. Chunsheng, D. Yali, J. Mingjie. 2004. Study on new health foods of Tartary buckwheat. In: Proceedings of the 9th International Symposium on Buckwheat. Prague: pp714-718.
- Bączek, N., Jarmułowicz, A., Wronkowska, M., & Haros, C. M. (2020). Assessment of the glycaemic index, content of bioactive compounds, and there in vitro bioaccessibility in oat-buckwheat breads. *Food Chemistry*, 127199.
- Jin, H. R., Yu, J., & Choi, S. J. (2020). Hydrothermal Treatment Enhances Antioxidant Activity and Intestinal Absorption of Rutin in Tartary Buckwheat Flour Extracts. *Foods*, 9(1), 8.
- Sprague, D. C. (2020). *Diabetes Champion Course no. 16-Lifestyle Management (1) Nutrition Guidelines*. 59MDW San Anotnio United States.
- Fatimah, O. R., Qamar, U. A., Zaiton, M. S., Shah, S. A. A., Latip, J., Alhassan, M. A., & Akilah, M. S. N. (2020). Assessment of free radical scavenging and digestive enzyme inhibitory activities of extract, fractions and isolated compounds from *Tetracera macrophylla* leaves. *Journal of herbal medicine*, 100351.
- Vaidehi, S., Prasath, G. S., Maheswari, J. U., & Rajasekar, N. (2020). HPLC identification of Rutin (3, 3', 4', 5, 7-pentahydroxyflavone-3-rhamnoglucoside) from *Costus pictus* leaves extract and evaluation of its antioxidant activity. *Asian Journal of Medical and Biological Research*, 6(2), 334-339.
- Rozanska, D., Mikos, K., & Regulska-Ilow, B. (2020). Assessment of the glycemic index of groats available on the Polish food market. *Roczniki Państwowego Zakładu Higieny*, 71(1).
- Peng, L., Zhang, Q., Zhang, Y., Yao, Z., Song, P., Wei, L., ... & Yan, Z. (2020). Effect of tartary buckwheat, rutin, and quercetin on lipid metabolism in rats during high dietary fat intake. *Food science & nutrition*, 8(1), 199-213.
- Gorjanović, S., Micić, D., Pastor, F., Tosti, T., Kalušević, A., Ristić, S., & Zlatanović, S. (2020). Evaluation of Apple Pomace Flour Obtained Industrially by Dehydration as a Source of Biomolecules with Antioxidant, Antidiabetic and Antiobesity Effects. *Antioxidants*, 9(5), 413.
- Ruan, J., Zhou, Y., Yan, J., Zhou, M., Woo, S. H., Weng, W., ... & Zhang, K. (2020). Tartary buckwheat: an under-utilized edible and medicinal herb for food and nutritional security. *Food Reviews International*, 1-15.
- Klepacka, J., Najda, A., & Klimek, K. (2020). Effect of Buckwheat Groats Processing on the Content and Bioaccessibility of Selected Minerals. *Foods*, 9(6), 832.
- Hasanein, P., Emamjomeh, A., Chenarani, N., & Bohlooli, M. (2020). Beneficial effects of rutin in diabetes-induced deficits in acquisition learning, retention memory and pain perception in rats. *Nutritional neuroscience*, 23(7), 563-574.
- Takasu, S., Parida, I. S., Ito, J., Kojima, Y., Eitsuka, T., Kimura, T., & Nakagawa, K. (2020). Intestinal absorption and tissue distribution of aza-sugars from mulberry leaves and evaluation of their transport by sugar transporters. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 68(24), 6656-6663.
- Ming, Y., Ma, Q. H., Han, X. L., & Li, H. Y. (2020). Molecular hydrogen improves type 2 diabetes through inhibiting oxidative stress. *Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine*, 20(1), 359-366.
- Sharmila, C., & Subramanian, S. P. (2020). Evaluation of Antidiabetic and Antioxidative Efficacy of *Strychnos Potatorum* (Nirmali) Seeds Extract in High Fat Diet Fed-Low Dose Streptozotocin Induced Experimental Type 2 Diabetes in Rats. *Diabetes*, 6(1), 1-8.
- Zhang, L., Ren, Q., & Chen, Q. (2020, July). Transcriptome Analysis on the Effect of Tartary Buckwheat Polysaccharide on the Liver of NAFLD-Model Mice. In *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Biological Information and Biomedical Engineering* (pp. 1-5).
- Zhou, Y., Jiang, Y., Shi, R., Chen, Z., Li, Z., Wei, Y., & Zhou, X. (2020). Structural and antioxidant analysis of Tartary buckwheat (*Fagopyrum tartaricum* Gaertn.) 13S

- globulin. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 100(3),
18. Witkowicz, R., Biel, W., Skrzypek, E., Chłopicka, J., Gleń-Karolczyk, K., Krupa, M.,

... & Galanty, A. (2020). Microorganisms and Biostimulants Impact on the Antioxidant Activity of Buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench) Sprouts. *Antioxidants*, 9(7), 584.